

Electrocardiography In Dogs and Cats

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Introduction

ECG is a three-letter acronym for Electrocardiography. The word is derived from electro (Greek for electricity), cardio (Greek for heart) and graph (Greek root meaning to write) It is a transthoracic interpretation of the electrical activity of the heart over time captured and externally recorded by skin electrodes. the device used to produce this non-invasive record is called the electrocardiograph. ECG is the gold standard for the noninvasive diagnosis of cardiac diseases and may occasionally be the only marker for the presence of heart disease.

Electrocardiograph

- Electrocardiograph (ECG machine) is a voltmeter (or galvanometer) that records the changing electrical activity of the heart between a positive and negative electrode.
- Electrocardiography is the process of recording this is electrical changes.

Indications for electrocardiogram

- Cardiac arrhythmias, Acute onset of dyspnoea, Shock., Fainting or seizures.
- Cardiac monitoring during and after surgery.
- Cardiac murmurs, Ventricular tachycardia, Cyanosis
- Cardiomegaly found on thoracic radiographs.
- Pre operatively in older animals.
- Evaluating the effect of cardiac drugs – especially quinidine and propranolol.
- Electrolyte disturbances, especially potassium abnormalities.
- Systemic diseases that affect the heart. Pericarditis, hydropericardium, myocardial inflammation, degeneration, valvular disease, Edema, tumors (heart base), Sinus bradycardia, Biventricular failure, right-sided congestive heart failure, left-side congestive heart failure, mitral valve problems (stenosis or insufficiency), congenital abnormalities.

- Chronic heart failure, cardiac arrest, systolic myocardial heart failure, pressure overload heart failure, volume overload heart failure
- Serial electrocardiograms as an aid in the prognosis and diagnosis of cardiac disease.

Basic electrophysiographic

- Automaticity: ability to initiate an impulse.
- Excitability: ability to respond to a stimulus.
- Conductivity: ability to transmit an impulse.
- Contractility: ability to respond with pumping action.
- Depolarization and repolarization of a cardiac cell generates action potential.
- ECG is the composite representation of action potential of all cardiac cell.

Electrical conduction system of the heart

- The electrical discharge for each cardiac cycle normally starts in a special area of the right atrium called the 'sinoatrial (SA) node'.
- Depolarization then spreads through the atrial muscle fibers. There is a delay while the depolarization spreads through another special area in the atrium, the 'atrioventricular (AV) node'.
- Thereafter, the electrical discharge travels very rapidly, down specialized conduction tissue: first a single pathway, the 'bundle of His', which then divides in the septum between the ventricles into right and left bundle branches.
- Within the ventricular mass, conduction spreads somewhat more slowly, through specialized tissue called 'Purkinje fibers'.
- Distal ventricular conduction system (Zidan, 2016).

Conduction speed of cardiac tissue

TISSUE	CONDUCTION RATE (M/S)
SA node	0.05
Atrial pathway	1
AV node	0.05
Bundle of his	0.05
Purkinje system	4
Ventricular muscle	1

Conduction of the impulse

- Normal resting membrane potential = -90mv.
- If the potential rises from -90 to 0, then this excites a further rise of potential, called the action potential. The action potential is transmitted throughout the cell and forms the impulse.
- During the rise of potential, the membrane becomes permeable to Sodium ions and the potential rises to a positive direction. This phenomenon is called depolarization.
- The Sodium channels close and there is rapid diffusion of K^+ ions into the exterior, reestablishing the resting membrane potential. This is called Repolarization. Repolarization is followed by muscle contraction and repolarization is followed by muscle relaxation.

Fig 1. depicting the mechanism of depolarisation and repolarization

Recording the electrocardiogram

The E.C.G Paper

- ECG machines record changes in electrical activity by drawing a trace on a moving paper strip.
- The electrocardiograph uses thermal paper, which is a graph paper & runs normally at a speed of 25mm/sec
- Time is plotted on the X axis & voltage is plotted on the Y axis.
- In X axis, 1 second is divided into 5 large squares each of which represents 0.2 sec. Each large square is further divided into 5 small squares which represents 0.04 sec.
- The ECG machine is calibrated in such a way that an increase of voltage by 1 mVolt should move the stylus vertically by 1cms.

Fig 2.

Positive and negative deflection in a lead

- A wave of electrical depolarization moves toward the positive pole of the - a+ ve deflection occurs

ECG Lead System

In animal body surface- limb ECG recording is used.

In human- mainly precordial (Chest) recording is used.

The three limb electrodes form a triangle called as Einthoven's Equilateral Triangle. (Benjamin Jin, 2012)

1. at the right arm (RA),
2. left arm (LA)
3. left leg (LL)

Preparation of animal for Dog

- Animal positioned in right lateral recumbency.
- No chemical restraint.
- Trained attendant or animal owner. (mudasi et al.,2014).

Electrodes /connectors - Crocodile clip

Connected to	Standard (colour)
Right fore limb	Red
Left fore limb	Yellow
Left hind limb	Green
Right hind limb	Black
Chest	White

Fig 3.

Six limb lead system

Bipolar standard leads-

- Lead I: Right arm (-) compared with Left (+) arm.
- Lead II: Right arm (-) compared with Left (+) leg.
- Lead III: Left arm (-) compared with Left (+) leg.
- PR Interval: From the start of the P wave to the start of the QRS complex.
- PR Segment: From the end of the P wave to the start of the QRS complex.
- QT Interval: From the start of the QRS complex to the end of the T wave.
- QRS Interval: From the start to the end of the QRS complex.
- ST Segment: From the end of the QRS complex to the start of the T wave.

Fig 4.

Elements of the ECG

Fig 5.

Fig 6.

0.2 sec.
ECG PAPER

Time and amplitude scale of ECG paper
 es in ECG graph- -small box- 0.1mV & 0.04 sec.
 -Larger box- 0.5mV & 0.2 sec.

Fig 7.

Normal ECG parameters

Measurements	Normal values
Heart rate	adult (70 – 160/min) Puppy (70 – 220/min)
P wave duration	(Width- 0.04 sec Giant breeds<0.05 sec)
P wave amplitude	Height - 0.4 mv
P – R interval	width-0.06 to 0.13 sec
QRS duration	<0.05 sec Giant breeds<0.06 sec
R wave amplitudes	<2.0 mV Giant breeds<2.5 mV
S – T segment	Depression (<0.2 mV) and Elevation (<0.15 mV)
T wave	<0.25 of normal R wave amplitude
Q – T interval	width -0.15 to 0.25 sec

Abnormal ECG parameter	Significance
Wide p wave	Left atrial enlargement.
Tall, peaked p waves	Right atrial enlargement,
P waves tall, wide and often notched	Bilateral atrial enlargement.
Wide QRS complexes, tall R waves	Left ventricular enlargement
Deep S waves in lead I, II, III	Right ventricular enlargement
Prolongation of P-R interval	Excessive vagal tone
S-T segment depression	Myocardial ischemia, acute myocardial ischemia, digoxin toxicity, electrolyte abnormalities, cardiac trauma
S-T Elevated	Myocardial infarction, pericarditis, myocardial hypoxia
Q-T segment prolongation	Hypokalemia, Hypocalcemia, Hypothermia
Q-T segment shorting	Hyperkalemia, Hypercalcemia

How to calculate Instantaneous Heart rate

Fig 8.

To calculate Heart Rate- (in beats per minute):

HR was calculated by successive R-R interval (Mukherjee, J. 2015)

HR (at 25 mm/s) = $1500/R - R \text{ interval (mm)}$

Ex. $1500/23 = 65.21$ beats per minute

At a paper speed of 50 mm/s, there is 3000mm per minute, thus:

HR (at 50 mm/s) = $3000/R - R \text{ interval (mm)}$

Calculating the average heart rate

Average heart rate ‘bic pen method’ At 25mm/sec. Start at 1 QRS complex

Count the number of QRS complexes during 6 sec=15cm =1 pen

Multiply by 10 At 50 mm/sec Start at 1qrs complex Count the number of QRS complexes during 3 sec =15cm =1 pen Multiply by 20

MEA (Mean Electrical Axis)

Average direction and magnitude of the depolarization wave through the ventricles are together termed the mean electrical axis (MEA) or cardiac axis (Martin, 2015). The main objective of determining the MEA is to establish criteria for ventricular dilatation or hypertrophy, and to detect intraventricular conduction defects. (daCosta CF, 2017). There are three common methods of calculating the MEA in the frontal plane. The Vector Method: Using leads I, II or III and the frontal plane diagram, calculate the algebraic sum of the QRS deflections in any two leads. The Largest Net Deflection Method.

The Isoelectric Method

The net amplitude in lead I is +4.5 (Q = -0.5 and R = +5). Plot 4.5 points along lead I in the hex axial lead system diagram and draw a perpendicular. The net amplitude in lead III is +22 (Q=-4 and R=+26). Plot 22 points along lead III and draw a perpendicular. Draw an arrow from the center to where the two perpendicular lines intersect. This is the direction of the MEA.

Normal canine MEA is 40-100 degree

ECG- Mean Electrical Axis (MEA)

Calculating MEA by graph

calculating the net deflection in lead I - graph on “X axis”

Calculating net deflection in lead AV - graph on “Y axis”

Draw the vector between the two (MEA)

MEA (mean electrical axis)

Largest Net Deflection Method.

- (i) Using all six limb leads and the hexaxial lead system, find the lead in which the QRS complexes have the greatest (positive) net amplitude – the MEA is approximately in this direction.
- (ii) Similarly, find the most negative complexes; the MEA is opposite in directions to this. The Isoelectric Method. Find the lead, in which the QRS complex is equally positive and negative (and usually small)-that is isoelectric lead. MEA will be perpendicular to this. find which of six limb leads that is perpendicular to the isoelectric lead. If the perpendicular lead is positive, then MEA is in this direction; if the perpendicular lead is negative, the MEA is in opposite direction to that lead.

Normal Sinus rhythm - A sequence of beats originating from the sino atrial node forms a rhythm, known as the sinus rhythm) Regular R-R interval ECG from a dog showing a normal sinus rhythm at a rate of 140/min (25 mm/sec and 10 mm/mV.)

Arrhythmia - Cardiac arrhythmias are defined as disturbances in rhythm and/or rate of heart, abnormalities of impulse formation and conduction Irregular R-R interval (Miller and Tilley, 1995).

Wandering atrial pacemaker - Wandering pacemaker characterizes by P' wave of varying amplitude and configuration. The rate of impulse originate, varies in the large sinus node (Boineu *et al.*, 1990).

Disturbance of sinus impulse formation sinus arrest- When there is a failure of the SA node to generate an impulse, that is, the SA node has temporarily arrested – it is referred to as sinus arrest. There is a pause in the rhythm with neither a P wave nor, therefore, a QRS–T complex, that is, the baseline is flat. then the blood pressure will fall and syncope will occur.

Sinus bradycardia -characterizes by heart rate less than 70 beats per minute without appreciable changes in R-R interval, Hyperkalemia, Hypoglycemia, Hypothyroidism, Hypothermia, enhanced parasympathetic tone as with: Increased inspiratory effort, Gastric irritation, Increased CSF pressure, More gap between R waves (Tilley,1985).

Sinus tachycardia- characterizes by regular sinus rhythm with a heart rate higher than 160 beats per

minute and is considered most common in dogs Rapidly coming R waves (Tilley, 1985).

Disturbance in supraventricular impulse formation

- **Atrial premature complexes** -premature atrial impulse originating from ectopic arterial site other than SA node. seen in dogs and cat with atrial enlargement, electrolyte disturbances, drug's reaction, congenital heart disease and neoplasia a normal variation in older animals.
- **Premature p wave** - QRS complexes are normal unless the p wave is so immature that it overlaps to varying degrees

Disturbance of ventricular impulse formation

- **Ventricular premature contractions (VPC)**. -Ventricular pre mature complexes are premature depolarization generated by an ectopic focus located in the ventricular tissue. (Cote and Ettinger, 2005). ECG Findings the QRS complexes are usually wide and bizarre. Artifacts
- **Muscle tremor artifact** -Movement artifact, Electrical interference.
- **Electrical alternans** -Alternation in the size of the QRS amplitude that occurs nearly every other beat.
- **Atrial fibrillations**-Normal QRS morphology. There are no consistent and recognizable P waves preceding the QRS complex. Ventricular heart rate is rapid and irregularly irregular.
- **Second degree av block**-Second-degree AV block occurs when conduction intermittently fails to pass through the AV node. The P wave is normal. occasional or a frequent failure (depending on severity) of conduction through the AV node resulting in the absence of a QRS complex
- **Complete (third) degree av block**- Complete AV block occurs when there is a persistent failure of the depolarization wave to be conducted through the AV node. P waves can be seen at a regular and fast rate, however, the QRS–T complexes are at a much slower rate and usually fairly regular. The P waves and QRS complexes occur independently of each other
- **Ventricular tachycardia**- Ventricular tachycardia is a series of three or more ventricular pre mature complexes occurring at a high rate. It may be continuous (sustained) or intermittent (paroxysmal) (Cote and Ettinger,2005).
- **Ventricular Fibrillation** - Depolarization waves occur chaotically and rapidly throughout the ventricles. Ventricular fibrillation (VF) is usually preceded by a very fast VT, typically with R-on-T. ECG characteristics. the ECG shows coarse (larger) or fine (smaller) rapid, irregular and bizarre movement with no normal waves or complexed.

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